

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)

Milestone 31 – Land Capability for Forestry Developments

Internal Note

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this Milestone report is to document developments in building the capabilities to assess climate change impacts and consequences on land and land use, specifically forestry, through the development of the Land Capability for Forestry (LCF) approach. The objective is to improve data integration and modelling capabilities to better understand what the capability of land may be to support forestry under future impacts of climate change. This informs the discussions on the development of net zero pathways in land and land use as addressed by the JHU-C3-1 Land Use Transformations project. Assessing the future land capability for forestry informs discussion developing net zero pathways. Such information is needed in the context of how climate impacts may affect land use change decisions and consequences on the multiple objectives for land, particularly the carbon sequestration or unintended sources of greenhouse gas emissions.

Improving approaches to understand the land’s capability for forestry is important due to legislated targets for woodland creation as part of the Scottish Government’s aims of achieving net zero.

These policy drivers operate within diverse cultural perspectives on land use, which when coupled with an emphasis on the need for ensuring food security, present challenges in land use transformations to meet multiple objectives. The development of the LCF has followed on from the development of the Land Capability for Agriculture (LCA) research platform.

1.1 Land Capability for Forestry Background

The Land Capability for Forestry (LCF) concept of assessing land for its capability to support forestry dates back to 1975 and was developed in the 1980’s into a method as a set of guidelines to be used by field surveys (Bibby et al 1988). The main use of the LCF was as an aid to decision-making at broad planning levels, as a guide for land managers and as a statement of the natural resources of the land of Britain in terms of forestry potential for educational and general interest purposes. It was used in the UK to identify where forestry could be established and for planning purposes, however it is important to note that the rationale at the time was for timber production purposes with few considerations if any of environmental impacts. This resulted in afforestation in the past on what would now be considered as inappropriate for today’s forestry objectives, e.g. planting on peatlands and consequences on carbon emissions.

The classification groups land according to limitations imposed by characteristics of soil, topography and climate on forestry. Land was assessed on its capability to produce tree crops under skilled forest management, which included cultivation, drainage, application of fertiliser and weed control where these are necessary. Both the LCF and LCA use a land capability class numbering system from 1 to 7 (where 1 is the best quality land and 7 the poorest), but several of the individual constraints [in the LCA](#) also use a 1 to 7 scale, for example the Climatic constraint. It is important to note that there is not a direct relationship between class and constraint values. The overall LCA and LCF classes are the value of the highest constraint value.

Table 1. Land Capability for Forestry class description (Bibby et al 1988).

Class	Description (for the growth and management of tree crops)
F1	Land with excellent flexibility
F2	Land with very good flexibility
F3	Land with good flexibility

F4	Land with moderate flexibility
F5	Land with limited flexibility
F6	Land with very limited flexibility
F7	Land unsuitable for producing free crops

The limitation types are:

- Climate*
- Windthrow
- Nutrients
- Topography*
- Droughtiness*
- Wetness*
- Soil*

The LCF method has a parallel approach alongside the Land Capability for Agriculture Classification system (LCA) (Bibby et al 1982). Note, those constraints methods marked * are common with the LCA, but the specific constraint parameters are different. Both systems use a capability class numbering system of 1 to 7, where 1 implies the best land and 7 as not suitable for either agriculture or forestry. However, the class numbers used in the two systems are not comparable, for example classes 1 to 3.1 in the LCA are considered Prime Agricultural Land (with associated use in National and Local Authority planning where there is a presumption against development) but there is no forestry equivalent. As such there is no direct mapping between, for example, LCA class 2 and LCF class 2. A revised version of the LCF (with proposed additions detailed below) will enable spatial analyses to assess better the relationships between land capability for agriculture and forestry.

The Land Capability platform has been updated with new soils and climate data and implemented as a new research platform¹. The ability to consider land capability for both forestry and agriculture using this platform facilitates improved analytical capabilities, with due consideration of relative strengths and weaknesses of the two approaches, in terms of helping to identify trade-offs in land uses and potential pathways to net zero.

The constraints of windthrow hazard and the role of soil nutrients are specific to the LCF. These are detailed in Section 3. The LCA and LCF methods share some common input data requirements and methods in terms of estimation and use of constraints to determine capability classes, though the specific parameters and derivation of constraint values are specific to the agriculture and forestry classes.

For forestry stand-level planning and species suitability assessments based on site specific soils and climate, the LCF approach was considered too coarse and was superseded by the Ecological Site Classification system (ESC) developed by Forest Research². However, there are challenges in meaningfully applying the ESC approach across regions or nationally where data limitations undermine its effectiveness. This makes it harder to address regional or national level questions about forestry and its role in broad land use and net zero pathway considerations. Hence there is a potential role for an updated LCF to consider forestry at a national level.

¹ [Updating Land Capability for Agriculture](#) – paper in review (January 2025)

² [Ecological Site Classification \(ESC\) - Forest Research](#)

1.2 Is the LCF fit for purpose?

The original LCF was developed when climate change, biodiversity and ecosystem services were not yet prominent issues of concern. The rationale for the LCF was to help inform decisions on increasing land use productivity for timber, but with few considerations of environmental impact, and paralleled the LCA focus on food production. This did not discourage the large areas of land planted for forestry, often with monocultures, particularly on peatland, that we would now consider as inappropriate due to consequences on ecosystem services (particularly climate regulation) and biodiversity. The increasing demand for land for multiple purposes now raises the question as to whether the original LCF method is fit for purpose given the current and future needs from forestry in Scotland integrated with other types of land use.

Whilst the rationale and motivations for forestry and associated policies and economics are very different now, the underlying concept of identifying land capability for forestry where productive woodland establishment is possible retains its utility. Land capability for forestry, at a fundamental level, remains a function of soil properties (depth, type, nutrients and water content), exposure (windthrow hazard) and climate interactions. The purpose of this Milestone is to explore how advances in data integration, modelling, spatial analyses and mapping can build on the existing LCF concept to support informed thinking and decision making under the current and future rationale for forestry.

This exploration considers the biophysical aspects of land capability for forestry and does not include any economic analysis. The LCF approach does not yet consider other risks such as from fire or susceptibility to tree diseases. Work within the SRP is developing a fire danger modelling system (D5-2) and there are opportunities to collaborate with the Plant Health Centre and Forest Research to explore how disease risks may be incorporated into the LCF.

1.3 Uncertainties in the future climate

There are uncertainties in estimating the future climate arising from several key sources including incomplete knowledge of the global climate system and data to parameterise climate models and the sensitivity of the climate to levels of atmospheric greenhouse gases and aerosols concentrations. Despite these issues, there is increasing certainty in the utility of climate models for foresight purposes as they have been shown to be able to represent regional climates sufficiently well in terms of estimates of precipitation and temperature to enable meaningful future impacts assessments and adaptation planning. In relation to the LCF however, wind speed and direction, usually associated with storm events, is less well represented.

1.3.1 Wind:

Climate models are improving their capability to estimate overall trends in climate by including greater understanding of the teleconnections between global influences such as the El Niño and La Niña cycle and other oscillations. Considerable effort has gone into projecting the future climate on a global scale under range of greenhouse gas emissions pathways and possible levels of radiative forcing ('greenhouse effect') by the climate modelling research community, there remain several key uncertainties related to forestry in Scotland. However, there remains uncertainty as to their ability to estimate windspeed and direction in UK storms. Most importantly, the key uncertainty is in the ability to estimate future wind conditions. Forestry is susceptible to storm events (e.g. storm Arwen in 2021) due to exposure to high windspeeds and frequent planting on shallow soils. It is worth noting that Storm Arwen caused substantial damage to Scotland and northern England's forests due to high winds from a northerly direction, which was unusual. Trees in the UK are generally more resilient (hardened off) to strong winds from south-westerly to north-westerly and easterlies.

Figure 1. Example of wind damage follow storm Arwen, November 2021.

Figure 1 illustrates windthrow damage following Storm Arwen (November 2021) which caused damage to c. 8,000 hectares and 16 million trees.

-Assessments of the data used in this report (see section 2.2) and associated research has indicated that the UKCP18 data, whilst covering a range of plausible climates, does not represent future wind speed and direction well. This presents challenges in modelling future land capability for forestry where windthrow hazard is a key determinant. This is significant because as global sea and land surface temperatures continue to rise, this will lead to an increase in the energy content of storms and hence higher windspeeds.

1.3.2 Precipitation and temperature

Research in previous Strategic Research Programmes has assessed the utility of the UKCP18 climate projections for estimating precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature. This found that at the original 12km granularity of the projections, that the data contained systematic biases and had a lack of spatial representation appropriate for land use and management considerations. A means and variance bias correction method was developed to reduce systematic biases and help make the climate projection data relevant at a 1km and daily time step resolution.

Whilst this approach has helped to reduce some spatial representation aspects of data use uncertainty, there remain uncertainties in the estimates of properties such as soil water balance that the input data are used for (e.g. estimate of soil moisture deficit and water table depths). The use of 12 climate projections (see SM2 Figure 2) helps to cover the range of possible future soil water conditions, however substantial challenges remain in calibrating and validating soil water balance models due to the lack of spatially representative observed data.

1.4 Forestry in a policy context

The current goal (2025) for afforestation is to increase new woodland creation to 18,000 hectares per year. There were approximately 15,000 hectares of new woodland planted in 2023-24, helping to increase woodland cover to 19%, with a goal of reaching 21% by 2032. It is worth noting that agroforestry is included as part of the woodland expansion strategy, but the LCF does not include representation of agroforestry. The subject of aligning tree species with soil types to avoid unintended consequences of increasing GHG emissions remains a subject of research interest (e.g. Matthews et al 2020). The existing LCF approach does not include consideration of carbon sequestration by trees or emissions impacts on soil processes arising from tree planting and subsequent growth (e.g. soil drying).

Woodland creation also features as part of Nature-based Solutions for flood management and biodiversity enhancement within the Scottish National Adaptation Plan. In 2025, Scottish Government and NatureScot will identify, prioritise and facilitate partnership projects for six large-scale landscape restoration areas with significant woodland components.

The UK is heavily reliant on timber imports at c. 73%, at a cost of c.£9 billion, hence there is interest in increasing national production. Timber products also have the potential to displace products associated with high GHG emissions, such as steel and concrete used in construction. These drivers are likely to increase pressures on land availability, along with those for food security, biodiversity enhancement and urban development.

Scotland's third Land Use Strategy (LUS3) sets out policies to achieve sustainable land use. Scotland's next Land Use Strategy (LUS4) is due for publication in 2026. Its aim is to address the Climate Change Committee's recommendation to provide an overarching strategy to outline the relationships and interactions between the multiple action plans and strategies relating to the broader environment. The challenges presented in how to achieve multiple benefits from land and land use whilst on a pathway to net zero require approaches such as the Land Capability platform to help inform policy development and strategic land use planning.

2 Activity

2.1 Land Capability Platform

The increased research capability presented here has been developed based on the creation of a new Land Capability Research Platform (LCRP), where the initial objective was to update the Land Capability for Agriculture (LCA) classification system (JHI-C3-1 Deliverable D6³ and JHI-C5-Large Scale Modelling).

The focus of efforts for this Milestone has been on developing the technical capability to utilise the LCF approach within the LCRP. The LCF and LCA share common data requirements and methods for determining the constraints that enable estimation of both the LCF and LCA class values. The platform is a data and modelling fusion approach, using up to date soils and climate data within a computer-based version of the LCA (Bibby et al 1982) and LCF guidelines (Bibby et al 1988).

The translation from guidelines into the new digital framework (coding Bibby et al 1982) used new soils and climate input datasets with increased precision (both temporal and spatial) to create a data integration pipeline (SM1 Figure 1). This means the framing and information content of the original LCA (e.g. the decision rules and output categories) are maintained as far as possible.

³ Paper in peer review, submitted December 2024 to Climatic Change Journal.

2.2 Datasets

The LCRP uses a range of input data sets including soils and climate (detailed below) for which a data pipeline has been developed (see SM1 Figure 1). Construction of this pipeline and data use within the platform has addressed the key challenges of integrating data sets, in a range of formats, at different spatial and temporal scales. These have been successfully used to generate a new version of the LCA under observed and future climates (Deliverable D6).

In terms of data for the LCF, there remains two key challenges to enable completion of the addition to the LCRP: develop a national coverage dataset for windspeed for the current and future climates to enable estimation of exposure to windthrow hazard; and develop an approach to use vegetation cover proxies where required to indicate soil nutrient conditions. The approaches considered for these issues are detailed here and in Section 3.

2.2.1 Climate data

For historical climate data (two periods of 1960-1989 baseline and 1990-2019), we used daily 1km resolution precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature data (HadUK-Grid 2024). This is an interpolated gridded surface from the UK Meteorological Office observation stations to provide complete and consistent coverage across the UK. Gradient is determined using a 5m Digital Elevation model (Ordnance Survey, 2022). We used the UKCP18 climate projections (UKCP18 2018). This daily 12km resolution daily data is estimated using the HadRM3 Regional Climate Model (CEDA 2021), with 12 future projections (ensemble members, EM) based on different parameterisations using RCP 8.5 (Moss et al 2010, Raihi 2017). This ensemble of future projections helps capture a range of possible climate responses to atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations (SM2 Figure 1). As detailed above, the original 12km projection data was bias corrected to a 1km resolution.

Whilst RCP8.5 is considered a high rate of emissions scenario, it reflects the continuous trend of increasing atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations (IEA 2021, NOAA 2022 UNFCCC 2024). Even if mitigation efforts are intensified and targets are reached, overall RCP8.5 based climate projections remain plausible given risks of positive feedback responses in natural systems and loss of climate regulation ecosystem services. Climate change levels are similar across the range of RCPs until divergence separates them more distinctly around 2050.

2.2.2 Soils data

High granularity estimates of individual constraints were estimated annually using unique soil-climate combinations (477,209 polygons in Scotland). Soil Series data are from a database of soil physical, hydrological and chemical properties (SSKIB, Soil Survey of Scotland Staff 2018) linked to 1:250,000 soils map (Soil survey of Scotland Staff, 1981). Within the LCRP issues arise where there are multiple soil series for the same soil-climate combinations, in which case the dominant soil series is used.

2.2.3 Importance of climate, water and energy in land capability

The key climatically determined constraints on land capability and therefore those most influenced by a changing climate, are energy and water inputs and soil water limitations (excess and deficit).

Since data for solar radiation as a source of energy input were not available for the original LCA and LCF methods, surveyors used thermal time accumulation (AT_0 base temperature = 0°C) between 1st January and end of June (Birse 1970 a, b) as a representation of energy input. In the LCF AT_0 (temperature above 5.6°C mean annual values) is used in conjunction with exposure (measured in mean annual wind speeds) provides the framework for assessing capability class, assisting correlation nationally. The use of daily interpolated observed and climate model temperature data at a 1km resolution in the LCRP has enabled high resolution estimation of AT_0 . It should be noted however, that satellite-based capabilities have

enable access to daily estimates of solar radiation at a resolution of c.4.5km (variable with latitude) from commercial organisations. We have acquired solar radiation data dating back to 1994 for the whole of Scotland. This has enabled improved evapotranspiration estimates which are subsequently used in soil water balance modelling and raises the potential for improved estimation of soil wetness suitability for forestry. It also raises the potential in the future to use as a direct estimate of energy input to vegetation growth, including forestry, though this will require the use of tree growth models.

To represent soil water limitations, the maximum Potential Soil Moisture Deficit (PSMD) was estimated (difference between precipitation and evapotranspiration, $n=30$ years). In the new LCRP, estimation of PSMD and soil wetness constraints uses a spatially applied soil water balance model (SM3). The median values of ATo and PSMD are combined to produce a single constraint value based on their position within climate class defining curves representing the range for warm and dry to cool and wet conditions (Figure 5 and SM1 Figure 1). In the LCF, droughtiness is assessed by subtracting the climatic water deficit from the soil's available water capacity and clearly reflects the interaction between climate and soil properties and the rooting depth. Soils with low water holding capacity would be severely constrained in the choice of trees species for planting.

The soil wetness constraint is based on soil profile properties (SM1 Table 2), water retention, plasticity and topsoil strength (primarily particle size and organic matter content), and is influenced by the climate. In assessing soil wetness, saturation of the root zone is determined from the length of days when the soil moisture is above field capacity. This information is accessed together with data which describes the soil's drainage properties. Information on soils which are seasonally flooded are also considered when assessment of the wetness limitation type of the LCF is being determined.

2.2.4 Assessing uncertainties in evapotranspiration and water availability:

The ability to accurately estimate reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) is a key issue as is used to estimate the maximum Potential Soil Moisture Deficit (PSMD) as used in the original LCA and LCF. It is also used as an input within a soil water balance model being tested as an alternative to estimating PSMD (see Supplementary material). PSMS is a climatic indicator of water availability and does not include consideration of soil properties and ability to retain water.

Reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) values can vary substantially depending on the calculation method employed, with Priestley-Taylor and Penman-Monteith approaches incorporating different atmospheric variables and assumptions. These methodological differences directly impact climatic water balance (CWB, difference between precipitation and ET_0) assessments, potentially leading to divergent conclusions about water availability. The comparison of these two methods reveals significant seasonal uncertainties in climatic water balance ($P-ET_0$) calculations across Scotland (Figure 2). While autumn and winter months (September through March) show strong agreement with predominantly blue regions indicating consistent surplus-to-surplus transitions, the summer half-year presents methodological divergence. May through July exhibit a complex spatial mosaic where yellow regions specifically indicate areas where the two methods disagree on the direction of change in climatic water balance. Eastern Scotland appears particularly affected by this methodological disagreement during summer months, while western regions show more consistency between methods. This seasonal pattern of divergence highlights the importance of careful method selection when assessing water balance in regions with strong seasonality, as the choice between Priestley-Taylor and Penman-Monteith can lead to contradictory conclusions about water availability trends.

Mean monthly climatic water balance change direction agreement between using Priestley-Taylor and Penman-Monteith over the period 1990-2019

Figure 2. Agreement maps for Priestley-Taylor and Penman-Monteith on the direction of change in mean monthly climatic water balance for the 1990 – 2019 period.

3 Constraint Maps

The constraint maps for soil wetness and climatic constraints used in the Land Capability platform (i.e. those methods and data inputs shared with the LCA) have been mapped as changes between the 1960-1989 baseline and future climate projections. Examples are provided here for two of twelve available UKCP18 projections.

3.1 Soil Wetness

The effect of soils wetness on land capability differs between land uses. For the LCA, trafficability, workability and poaching risk are the principal effects of wetness on the arable land and grassland. In forestry, soil wetness limitation is a vital component of windthrow hazard and presenting as a physiological barrier to root growth in areas where windthrow hazard is reduced i.e. in sheltered zones. In soils with a large water store, e.g. Peat together with strong acidity presents conditions suitable for a very limited range of trees. In addition, topographic limitations are adjusted for slope stability based on the wetness characteristic of the topsoil.

Climate change will likely alter the soil wetness values through the influence of changes in temperature and precipitation and consequences on evapotranspiration. Examples of the soil wetness constraint under a climate projection compared to the use of 1960-1989 interpolated observed baseline climate data are provided in Figures 3 and 4. These examples show there is spatial variation in the changes in soil wetness constraint, associate with potentially reduced water availability (shown as yellow) meaning an increase in constraint and therefore possible reduction in LCF class (with other constraints also determining the overall class. The green areas indicate a reduction in soil wetness constraint, indicating a higher potential for woodland creation, though other factors such as windthrow hazard also need to be considered. Figures 3 and 4 also indicate areas where there has been no change in wetness constraint, however windthrow risk may have increased due to higher windspeeds. The completion of the LCF within the LCRP will integrate the range of constraints.

Figure 3. Land Capability Soil Wetness constraint change between the 1960-1989 baseline period and the simulated 2020-2049 future projection (04). Note: Increased constraint refers to an increase in level of constraint; Reduced constraint refers to a decrease; No change means the level of constraint remains the same between the two time periods.

Figure 4. Land Capability Soil Wettness constraint change between the 1960-1989 baseline period and the simulated 2050-2079 future projection (04). Note: degraded refers to an increase in level of constraint; upgraded refers to a decrease; No change means the level of constraint remains the same between the two time periods.

3.1.1 Climate Constraint

Figure 5. Land Capability Climate Constraint for the 1960-1989 baseline period. Note: The scale of 1-7 for the climate constraint is not the same as the Land Capability for Agriculture 1-7 classification – see text.

Figure 6. LCF Climate constraint map for the Baseline climate reference (1960 – 1990).

Figure 5 shows the LCA climate constraint (estimated with updated climate data from the original version), which enables comparison with the LCF climatic constraint in Figure 6. The climatic constraint is

regarded as the key framework for the LCF classes and serves as a primary delimiter of the best possible capability class. Any further adjustment will be necessary according to other guidelines on limitation. The potential capability class is estimated from equations defining the relation curves between exposure and accumulated temperature and jointly interpreted with the box chart (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Changes in the climatic constraint of the LCF climate factor between 1960 – 1989 and 1990 – 2019 climate periods. Increased constraint refers to an increase in level of constraint; reduced constraint refers to a decrease; No change means the level of constraint remains the same between the two periods.

3.1.2 Exposure

The original LCF used topographic exposure, assessed by summing the angles of inclination of the skyline at the eight major points of the compass at any site ('Topex' method) as part of the estimation of wind throw hazard. A measure of the atmospheric warmth, using accumulate temperature (AT_0) and exposure are combined to provide an interpretation in terms of forestry capability classes, shown in Figure 8 as the original LCF map used.

The original windthrow hazard class was estimated based on the Detailed Aspect Method of Scoring (DAMS) scores and the soil type. However, as detailed below, Forest Research have disregarded the use of a windthrow hazard class and introduced a new windiness risk indicator. This approach uses the DAMS to predict a Critical Wind Speed (CWS at canopy top) and manipulate this CWS for a probability of damage to Forest stands.

Figure 8 The original Land Capability for Forestry Accumulated Temperature (AT_0) and Exposure map (Bibby et al 1988).

The CWS can be converted to corresponding wind speed at 10m above zero plane displacement for it to be used with meteorological data to calculate probability of occurrence and return period.

It should be noted however that climate models may have less skill in estimating future windspeeds than say, contiguous variables such increases in temperature. Climate projections however do indicate an increasing probability of higher windspeeds in storms, which may become more frequent.

Land Capability for Forestry estimates for Accumulated Temperature and Exposure relative to Forestry Capability class (1960 - 1990) climate reference

Figure 9. New exposure map based on original method using updated accumulate temperature and windspeed estimates based on the relationship between land cover (surface roughness) and DAMS.

3.2 Wind throw hazard

The Windthrow hazard classification (WHC) (Miller, 1985) used the rooting depth and local topographic shelter to predict the height at which possible damage from wind would be expected within thinned and unthinned forest stands. The weighting of these two key aspects determining a Windthrown hazard are subjective being based on expert's judgements and observed damage. The Quine and White, (1993) approach to the WHC used a multiple regression model on the rate of attrition of tatter flags against elevation, topographic exposure, aspect, and wind zone categorisation. A scoring which is based on the relative weights of these model elements resulted in the Detailed Aspect Method of Scoring (DAMS). DAMS reduces the subjectivity in the WHC, and it is available for Scotland at a 50m resolution, providing a practical method for estimating the windiness over a large area. However, windiness estimates are heavily influenced by proximity to sites where attrition rates from tatter flags were available (Suarez et al., 1999).

DAMS does not account for surface roughness associated with different land cover types (open/ forested areas) which may alter the windiness conditions at particular land cover types (Hannah, 1993, Hale et al., 2015). In developing the LCF classification, a windiness map has been produced (Figure 10) across Scotland considering the surface roughness of the land. Using the Forestry Commission's Sub-Compartment data on forest holdings and DAMS the above-canopy wind speed was computed. Once this can be validated, the windiness maps can be converted to wind risk for forest land capability classification. Current research, ForestGALES (Gardiner et al., 2004, 2008), uses the windiness of an area and the probability of a Critical Wind Speed (CWS) being exceeded and resulting in an overturning or breaking of trees in a forest stand as a replacement for the WHC. The application of the ForestGALES model requires an accurate knowledge of the local wind speed (Suarez et al., 1999) which may limit its application on a regional scale forest capability classification considering windthrow hazard as a limitation for forest land capability.

As detailed in Section 1.3.1, there remains uncertainty in the utility of future climate projections for wind speed. A challenge to address having developed the LCRP to this stage is therefore to explore how Critical Wind Speed values can be usefully estimated from existing climate model data and, or, addition to existing windspeed data.

Figure 10. Wind speed category determined from Detailed Aspect Method of Scoring (DAMS).

3.2.1 Soil nutrients

Although the application of fertilisers, principally phosphorus (P) and potassium (K), is part of regular forest practice, trees rely far more on the natural availability of nutrients than do farm crops. The presence of these soil nutrients, as well as nitrogen (N) is often indicated by the occurrence of certain plant species in the pre-planting vegetation cover. On organic soils, nutrient availability has been related to the total content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. Much of the original LCF in respect of nutrients was focussed on nutrient limitations on peat soils, however, given the recognition of the value of peatlands for carbon and water storage, there is less of an emphasis on the need to assess LCF in these locations. On mineral soils, nutrient availability is related to the volume of soil available for rooting and to the chemical composition of the parent material.

Data for N, P and K are not available spatially from the Scottish Soils Survey database, as they are highly variable over space and time.

In the current development of the LCF, explorations have been made on the potential of using land cover and, or vegetation mapping to be used as a proxy indicator of soil nutrients through the association with presence of plant species. This approach requires further development but holds opportunities in respect of also helping to overcome the issue of estimating the consequences of climate change on species composition and ecological function. This opportunity arises from on-going research elsewhere in the SRP (JHI-D5-2) considering the use of the Ellenburg Indicator values that have been developed to classify species' habitat niches and the types of habitat conditions which contain their peak occurrences (Ellenberg 1988). The concept here is based on species composition at a site can be displayed as the species distributions along an environmental gradient, then the relative positions of species in that environmental gradient can be visualised, both for current and future climates.

Further research is required to determine if this is a variable alternative to the original approach to incorporating soil nutrients within the LFC. A further aspect that also requires further consideration is the probability that climate change will alter the soil processes, particularly soil water movements (vertical and lateral flows) and microbial activity that determine the type and availability of nutrients.

3.2.2 Topography

Slope is an important topographic element in the determining forest land capability. As an effect from topography, mechanised operation can be heavily limited for successfully establishing forestry. Ploughing at slopes less than 35° on dry stable slopes or 30° on slopes where the topsoil is wet may be possible, other than mounted ploughs, these limits are significantly reduced (5° –18°). Local topographic variations (e.g. slopes with rocky or bouldery patterns) may present modification to the overall LCF class.

Figure 11 presents the slope limits and soil stability categorization for estimating LCF topographic limitations type.

Topographic categorisation for the estimating LCF limitation types

- Slope limit categories
- slope 18 -30 with wet soils
 - slope 18 -35 with dry soils
 - slope 5-18
 - slope < 5
 - slope > 35

Figure 11. Slope limits and soil stability categorization for estimating LCF topographic limitations type.

4 Assessment of the utility of the LCF approach

Forestry remains a key part of Scotland's land use mosaic, with a requirement to increase woodland area for carbon sequestration and timber production given the importance of replacing GHG intensive materials, such as those used in construction, with products that can store carbon for long periods. There is need for a balanced approach to as achieving multiple objectives from land (food security, biodiversity enhancement and Nature restoration), rather than an optimisation for a single outcome. As such the LCF has an important role to play in informing how that balance can be achieved.

However, the LCF in its current form has limited value for planning woodland creation in the context of policy aims to achieve multiple objectives from land and land use. This is primarily due to the method lacking wider ecosystem services considerations having been developed at a time when the economic and ecological rationale for forestry was very different from today. This does not imply the LCF does not have value as a tool to fit alongside other land use research approaches such ecological restoration zonation (e.g. Gimona and Castellazzi 2025), but it is important to recognise its limitations in the current need for tools that take a wider ecosystem services perspective.

A similar conclusion on utility has been drawn on the original Land Capability for agriculture classification system, though for the LCA the fundamental approach continues to have greater relevance to agriculture and land value.

To overcome this limitation in the LCF there needs to be additional elements built into the method to:

- Enable inclusion of the net balance in greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration over time periods relevant to GHG inventory and policy reporting periods.
 - This requires inclusion of modelling of impacts on soil functions and soil water.
 - To enable comparison of benefits and trade-offs with other forms of land use, this needs to be spatial, to understand the GHG balance over time considering unique soil-climate combinations.
- Include impacts of woodland creation on biodiversity.
- Integrate with other woodland planning and modelling tools, for example those developed by Forest research.

5 Further steps

In terms of assessing the exposure and windthrow hazard aspects of the land capability for forestry under climate change, the key challenge is in developing access to and utilising of appropriate wind speed and direction data for future climate projections. Whilst the use of the ForestGales data has the potential to inform consideration of windthrow risk in the current climate, decisions on woodland creation needs to consider future conditions on a 40-60 plus year horizon. Climate change impacts are likely to affect vegetation-soil interactions resulting in changes in the relationships between presence of species indicating soil nutrients. This implies the current potential use of species to indicate soil nutrition may not necessarily be valid for future conditions. Options to address this include using climate envelopes to assess spatial changes. There is also a need to improve soil depth data to enable more accurate constraint estimation. A further uncertainty is how climate change will affect nitrogen deposition, which is a key nutrient input to otherwise nutrient poor locations in Scotland. This is being assessed in the SRP D1 and D5-2 projects.

Further research and engagement with Forest Research colleagues, will explore approaches to simulating future windspeed above the Critical Wind Speed (CWS) and direction data to enable estimations of

exposure and windthrow risk. This can be integrated with up to date soils data, particularly soil depths, to improve assessment of windthrow risk.

Once these challenges have been overcome, then coding of the LCF constraints (building on the existing LCA structures) can be relatively straightforward. This will enable the digital re-creation of the original LCF method, updated with new soils and climate data and revised constraint estimation methods. However, as noted above, this will not enable assessment of GHG balances of carbon loss and storage in newly created woodlands, ecological function (i.e. consequences on hydrology) or biodiversity aspects of land capability for forestry. These are elements that have the potential to be introduced as part of an overall increase in the Land Capability Research Platform functions.

Addition of the further elements above will enhance the utility of the LCF, however these need to be developed in conjunction with improvements in the LCA approach to help increase comparability between forestry and agriculture land capability assessments. In developing the LCF and LCA, the research team are formulating an improved understanding of how the Land Capability Research Platform can be developed in the future to enable a better incorporation of new data, constraint estimation and integration of land use objectives. This will help improve capabilities to understand better the trade-offs between land use and need to achieve multiple objectives.

6 References

- Bibby JS, Douglas HA, Thomasson AJ, Robertson JS (1982). Land Capability Classification for Agriculture. Macaulay Land Use Research Institute. Aberdeen.
- Bibby JS, Heslop, REF, Hartnup R (1988) Land Capability for Forestry in Britain. The Macaulay Land Use Research Institute, Aberdeen. ISBN 0 7084 0467 7
- Birse EL (1970a) Assessment of Climatic Conditions in Scotland 3. The Bioclimatic sub-regions. Aberdeen. Macaulay Institute for Soil Research.
- Birse EL (1970b) Climatic Assessment and Land Use Capability. Practical Applications of Soil Survey. Proceedings of the Stirling Field Meeting, Aberdeen. Macaulay Institute for Soil Research.
- CEDA (2021) Met Office Hadley Centre Regional Climate Model (HadRM3-PPE). [Dataset Collection Record: Met Office Hadley Centre Regional Climate Model \(HadRM3-PPE\) Data \(ceda.ac.uk\)](#)
- Ellenberg, H. (1988) Vegetation ecology of central Europe. Cambridge University Press.
- Gardiner, B.A., Suarez, J., Achim, A., Hale, S.E., Nicoll, B.C., 2004. ForestGALES 2, A PC-based Wind Risk Model for British Forests. User Guide. Forestry Commission, Edinburgh.
- Gardiner, B.A., Byrne, K., Hale, S.E., Kamimura, K., Mitchell, S., Peltola, H., Ruel, J.-C., 2008. A review of mechanistic modelling of wind damage risk to forests. *Forestry* 81, 447- 463.
- Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M. (2025) Transformative landscape change to tackle the climate and biodiversity crises: a Scotland-wide zonation for restoration (v.1.1). RESAS Research Program 2022-27, grant JHI-C5-1, Deliverable 3.2-Landscape Zonation.
- Hannah, P. (1993). Application of Wind Modelling techniques in complex terrain. PhD Thesis, University of East Anglia, Norwich, UK.
- Matthews, K.B.; Wardell-Johnson, D.; Miller, D.G.; Fitton, N.; Jones, E.; Bathgate, S.; Randle, T.; Matthews, R.B.; Smith, P.; Perks, M. (2020) Not seeing the carbon for the trees? Why area-based targets for establishing new woodlands can limit or underplay their climate change mitigation benefits., *Land Use Policy*, 97, Article No. 104690.
- Quine, C.P., White, I.M.S., 1993. Revised Windiness Scores for the Windthrow Hazard Classification: the Revised Scoring Method. Information Note No. 230. Forestry Commission, Edinburgh.
- Soil Survey of Scotland Staff (2018). Scottish Soils Knowledge and Information Base (SSKIB). Version 1.1. 10.5281/zenodo.5566700.
- Suarez, J.C., Gardiner, B.A., Quine, C.P., 1999. A comparison of three methods for predicting wind speeds in complex forested terrain. *Meteorology. Applications* 6, 329-342.

7 Supplementary Material 1: Land Capability Platform

SM1 Figure 1. Schematic of the Land Capability data fusion and research framework.

The analytical framework was developed from guidelines of the original LCA (Bibby et al., 1982) and its visualization will be implemented as a web-based platform. Each modular process of the platform estimates the biophysical and soil-climate interaction processes including drought, soil wetness, relief, erosion and flood risk from which an overall limitation is estimated, and the land classified based on the most limiting of these biophysical factors.

The methodology for determining the land capability classes is described in Supplementary Material 6 (the original document Bibby et al., 1982), however, ambiguities in the documentation and expectations of surveyor expertise-based inputs makes it difficult to completely implement the original methodology as documented. Gaps in the available digital input datasets were also limiting and alternative approaches in some cases had to be implemented. For example, there are data gaps on incidence of crop damage necessitating re-drilling and crop yield penalties which are required for the LCA erosion risk assessment. This was substituted with an assessment of the land capability based on exposure to the coast and susceptibility to wind erosion.

No flood risk assessment for LCA class determination was implemented in this study because information on damaging flooding in the original method was based on field surveyors' visual assessment and discussions with landowners, no comparable digital information on flooding in agricultural land was available. Future developments of the platform will try to incorporate up to date flood risk mapping.

Accumulated temperature and PSMD are representations of the fundamental requirements of energy and moisture which is required by plants for photosynthesis. Our method applied modelled soil moisture

deficit (SMD) estimated using a soil water balance model (SM3) instead of the theoretical deficit between precipitation and evapotranspiration. The rationale was to enable soil-climate unique combination specific PSMD estimates.

We implemented the Priestly-Taylor (Priestley and Taylor, 1972) method to calculate the reference evapotranspiration (ET_o), considered for a grass sward with ample water supply. The Priestley-Taylor method is suited to estimate evapotranspiration from a limited sets of input variables and was particularly useful in this case due to the lack of relative humidity and wind speed data required to implement the Penman-Monteith equation (Monteith, 1965). Potential evapotranspiration was calculated for each 30 years climate slice (1960-1989, 1990-2019, 2020 -2049 and 2050-2079) from 1km gridded observation (1960-2019) and the UKCP18 climate projections (2020 – 2079) comprising 13 climate ensembles for the climate projections respectively.

Accumulated temperature above 0°C was calculated for the growing season (January - June) and combined with the SMD to determine a climatic class. In our attempt be consistent with the original method used to determine the climate classes, we defined a set of equations which best fits the original regression equation.

Soil wetness and droughtiness components of the LCA both represent a complex interaction between soil and climate. Soil droughtiness is accessed by calculating the available soil water reserve within the depth likely to be exploited by the plant and subtracting from this value, the excess of the PSMD over the growing season. Soil wetness is accessed on the climatic environment, soil water regimes and the textural properties of the topsoil. The principal effect of this assessment is on the workability, trafficability and poaching risk with climatic regime mainly relating to the length of field capacity period (Bibby et al., 1982).

In this study, we present an approach of calculating the field capacity period which differs from the original methodology (Bibby et al 1982).

Since our approach modelled soil water balance (i.e. soil moisture deficit) using a simple bucket model adjusted for different soil types based on the water holding capacity, we applied the concept of return-to, and end-of field capacity days to determine the length of field capacity days (Francis 1981). For each year over the 30 years climate reference period, dates when the soil moisture content fell below or attained field capacity was determined and applied to calculate length of field capacity days. Periods of return-to or end-of field capacity were taken as dates after 5 consecutive days of moisture deficit less than 5mm (return to field capacity) or greater than 5mm (end of field capacity). Both end of field capacity and the return to field capacity were differentiated over each year to calculate the length of field capacity and the median value over the climate period applied to estimate the soil wetness class and the climate and soil assessments leading to capability classes.

SM1 Table 3 Differences between the original classification input data.

Inputs	Original LCA	Computing platform
Climate data	Limited number of meteorological stations with 20-year records for precipitation, temperature (1958-78) and wind (1965-73), whilst wetness classes based on 1941-71.	1km resolution daily spatially interpolated observed precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature (1960-2019), solar radiation (derived from satellite observations for 1994-2019, and estimated using Machine Learning from 1960-1994), wind (MORECS ⁴ covering 1960-2017).

⁴ [Meteorological Office Rainfall and Evaporation Calculation System \(MORECS version 2.0\) - Catchment Management Modelling Platform \(ceh.ac.uk\)](http://ceh.ac.uk)

		There have been detectable changes in the climate since the 1958-78 original period.
Estimation of climatic constraints	Accumulated temperature (<i>ATo</i>) and maximum potential soil moisture based on limited climatic data. Soil wetness class was generally based on field observations.	<i>ATo</i> and maximum PSMD estimated using a daily time step soil water balance model and 1km resolution daily time-step climate data. Soil wetness classes estimated from soil water balance model run using soil database details.
Potential soil moisture deficit (PSMD)	This was a climatic constraint only and used an 'ideal' soil (loamy, free draining, no limitation to water) and had simplistic 'bucket' approach to calculate evaporation.	1km resolution precipitation and Reference Evapotranspiration used to estimate Climatic Water Balance on a daily basis, to determine the maximum PSMD.
Soils data	1:250,000 soil series maps	National Soils Inventory / SSKIB database, based on original 1:250,000 soil series, updated through resampling and generation of additional properties through pedotransfer functions.
Topography	Ordnance Survey relief maps (50m contours)	OSTerrain5 Digital Elevation Model resampled at 100m resolution for gradient analysis. Note: currently no areas above any specified elevation have been excluded e.g. mountain tops.
Guideline application	Based on surveyors skillfully applying the guidelines in an objective way (hence standardisation between surveyors).	Guidelines implemented within computer code, but it has not been possible to factor in the human 'on-site checking' element. Some text descriptions and structures of the assessment of the physical factors cannot be directly converted to computer code.

The platform data integration allows soil data provided at 1:250 000 scale from the Scottish Soil and Knowledge Information Base (SSKIB) to be joined to climatic variables at a 1km grid cell resolution and daily time step and can be manipulated for over 477,209 unique soil identities that comprised the 580 distinct soil map units in Scotland.

8 Supplementary Material 2: Climate Data

The results presented are based on the use of the UKCP18 Climate Projections. This data is estimated using a UK Meteorological Office Regional Climate Model (HadRM3) (CEDA 2021)⁵. There are 12 different projections of the future climate made using this model, providing 12 unique data sets (also referred to as Ensemble Members). Each projection is based on the same emissions scenario (below) but with slightly different model settings. This was done to capture the range of possible climate responses to the level of atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations resulting from the emissions scenario. Each of the twelve HaDRM3 simulations is referred to as an 'Ensemble Member' (EM).

To aid interpretation of results, it is important to understand the differences between the ensemble members' data in respect of their temperature and precipitation differences from the past climate (1960-1989). This is illustrated in SM2 Figure 1, showing the differences (anomaly) between ensemble members for the two future time periods used: 2020-2049 and 2050-2079, with respect to the 1960-1989 baseline

⁵ [Dataset Collection Record: Met Office Hadley Centre Regional Climate Model \(HadRM3-PPE\) Data \(ceda.ac.uk\)](https://ceda.ac.uk/dataset-collection-record/met-office-hadley-centre-regional-climate-model-hadrm3-ppe-data)

period. For example, ensemble member 07 has a 1.4°C temperature increase by the 2040s period, but the same precipitation amount compared to the baseline period (i.e. no change). By the 2070s, ensemble member 07 becomes 2.5°C warmer and has 5% less precipitation. In contrast, ensemble member 13 is 2.1°C warmer and 9% drier by the 2040s, and 3°C warmer and 21% drier by the 2070s.

SM2 Figure 1 Precipitation and temperature anomaly for the bias corrected UKCP18 climate projections compared to the 1960-189 baseline period for the whole of Scotland.

SM2 Figure 1 shows the differences between the climate projections' data in respect of their temperature and precipitation differences from the past climate (1960-1989) for 2020-2049 and 2050-2079, with respect to the 1960-1989 baseline period. This study has used three projections EM04, with an overall increase of 2°C mean temperature increase, EM06 has a 4% increase in mean annual total precipitation and EM13 a c.2.5% decrease.

8.1 Bias Correction method applied to UKCP18 climate projections

For each climate variable and all ensemble members, an improved version of the Rivington et al (2008a) bias correction (BC) methodology was applied spatially, partially downscaling from the HadRM3-PPE Regional Climate Model (RCM) at a 12 km resolution to a 1 km grid. It follows the basic principle employed by others in identifying errors in hindcast estimates and correcting them as far as possible, then applying the same BC to future projections.

Briefly there are two stages:

1. Evaluating and bias correcting ensemble members' hindcasts. For precipitation this means a) correcting the number of rain days using a Rain Day Threshold (RDT), i.e. the amount that needs to be subtracted from all rainfall events so the mean number of rain days match and 2) a correction to match the Mean Annual Total (MAT). For Tmax and Tmin, month specific corrections to mean (additive) and variance (multiplicative) differences were made. Comparison between observed (1km) and RCM (12km) data followed by BC partially downscales the modelled data by adding localised spatial variability but maintains the RCM synoptic patterns.

2. Bias correcting future projections uses the hindcast corrections applied to modelled future values. This corrects for biases in the modelling of the climate processes within the parent GCM and the HadRM3 RCM, i.e. modelling error (Murphy et al. 2004), and differences between the characteristics of the RCM grid and the specific 1×1 km cell (i.e. representation error), but does not address scenario uncertainty from future emissions assumptions.

Mapping the BC correction values identifies the nature, magnitude, location and seasonal distribution of corrections applied for every 1×1 km cell in the UK. Mapping correction values identifies combinations of climate variable and locations where the RCM either does or does not represent well the observations. The relative magnitude of errors, set against either the observed phenomena or future change, is a useful way of assessing where caution should be exercised in the use of particular location-variable combinations from the RCM data (Moberg and Jones, 2004). Mapping may also have value in interpreting patterns of correction values by suggesting linkages with spatial phenomena that influence climate such as altitude, proximity to the sea, land covers such as large urban areas etc.

A previous study by the authors made comparisons only using a single RCM scenario at individual locations (Rivington et al. 2008b). Use of the RCM ensemble allowed us to assess if patterns of bias were consistent between members either thematically or spatially. Comparing the correction values between ensemble members gives a better understanding of the degree of knowable uncertainty within the ensemble as a whole. Comparisons between ensemble members may also provide insights into the effect of different assumptions and parameterisations within RCM runs and reflect the range of skill of the parent GCM.

Bias Correction References:

Moberg A, Jones PD (2004) Regional climate model simulations of daily maximum and minimum near-surface temperatures across Europe compared with observed station data 1961–1990. *Clim Dynam* 23: 695 – 715

Rivington M, Miller D, Matthews KB, Russell G, Bellocchi G, Buchan K (2008a) Downscaling regional climate model estimates of daily precipitation, temperature and solar radiation data. *Clim Res* 35(3): 181-202

Rivington M, Miller D, Matthews KB, Russell G, Bellocchi G, Buchan K (2008b) Evaluating regional climate model estimates against site-specific observed data in the UK. *Climatic Change* 88 (2): 157-185

Murphy JM, Sexton DMH, Barnett DN, Jones GS, Webb MJ, Collins M, Stainforth DA (2004) Quantification of modelling uncertainties in a large ensemble of climate change simulations. *Nature* 430: 768–772

9 Supplementary Material 3: Soil Water Balance Modelling

To estimate soil water balance we used a simple model based on rates of evapotranspiration and infiltration. This model was developed from an original approach that aligned with the level of data available and methods used in the Land Capability for Agriculture classification system. This revised model was used to estimate Field Capacity Days (FCD) and maximum Potential Soil Moisture Deficit (PSMD) in the LCA.

SM3 Table 1 Lists the definitions for the soil water terms used in the Soil Water Balance modelling.

SP	Saturation Point	The point at which a soil can receive no more water
FC	Field Capacity	The amount of water soil can hold against the force of gravity -0.033MPa; -1/3bar; pF 2.53; -10 (sand) to -33 (clay) J/kg; -50cm pressure head
WP	Wilting Point	Moisture content of soil at which plants start to wilt (water difficult to extract)
PWP	Permanent Wilting Point	Moisture content of soil at which plants will fail to recover from wilting -1.5MPa; -15bar; pF 4.18; -1500J/kg; -15300cm pressure head
AWC	Available Water Capacity	Field Capacity minus Permanent Wilting Point
EAWC	Easily Available Water Capacity	Field Capacity minus Wilting Point
AD	Air Dried	Lowest amount of water possible without oven drying

SM3 Figure 1 Terminology used in the estimation of the soil moisture critical points.

9.1 Soil Water Balance Model

This Soil Water Balance model improves upon the model developed by L.P. Smith of the Met Office (MAFF 1967, 1971) and used in Met. Office (1981).

The previous system defined 125mm of water as available for extraction in 3 layers. The first layer of 50mm is available at 100% of the potential evapotranspiration rate. The second layer of 50mm is available at 50% of the rate. The third is available at 25%. No further water can be removed from the soil. Rainfall is added to the topmost layers that are below capacity during refill irrespective of the total soil moisture deficit.

It was noted that “the assumed maximum deficit of 125mm is likely to be an overestimate...in the rough grazing lands”; furthermore “the major source of error probably lies in the assumption of a 125mm maximum. The true value is bound to be a function of soil type and depth” (MAFF 1971). The paper acknowledged that the monthly or fortnightly time intervals introduced errors that could be reduced with a finer resolution. The MAFF model did not specify the critical points of soil moisture (i.e. Field Capacity); instead it concentrated only on the available water capacity. This model improves the MAFF system by:

- Varying soil available water according to soil conditions (depth and texture)
- Dynamically set the layer thresholds (maintaining ratios from original model)
- Model soil moisture on a daily time-step
- Model Surplus Water Above FC and (as described in Met Office memo 108) drain any excess after 3 days
- Introduction of a fourth “layer” below PWP where we can evaporate down to the “air dried” point

There are two stages to the model:

- Stage 1 - Daily Water Balance

- Stage 2 - Soil Water Balance

SM3 Figure 2 Soil Water Balance Model structure. Numbers in yellow circles refer to the steps in calculation procedure detailed in SM3 Figure 3.

The following describes the order of operation:

- At point 1 P is balanced against ETo. This results in runoff when SP is exceeded. Remaining P becomes Water Above FC.
- At point 2 the Water Above FC attempts to service the ETo requirement; with any surplus attempting to enter the soil. Any surplus Water Above FC becomes drainage.
- At point 3 the Water Above FC attempts to service the ETo requirement; with any surplus attempting to enter the soil. Any further surplus Water Above FC moves to the next Water Above FC container.
- At point 4 water attempts to enter the soil. Any surplus Water Above FC moves to the next Water Above FC container.

- ET at point 5 occurs when there remains un-serviced ETo, the system is below FC and, by definition, there is no Water Above FC remaining. Extraction is from the top-most soil moisture layer first. The ET extracted from layers 2 and 3 is at the lower rates of 50% and 25% respectively. ET continues in layer 4 at the rate of 25%. Water cannot be extracted from layer 5 (i.e. when soil is air dried).

Note: the use of mm here is shorthand for the unit "mm per 1000mm soil depth" - the examples assume a soil depth of 1m; thus SP=600mm indicates that the oven dried soil content is 400mm. To represent a soil horizon of 500mm then we would scale those amounts so that SP=300mm and the oven dried soil is 200mm.

The following soil input parameters are required by the model:

- D : Soil Depth
- SP : Saturation Point
- FC : Field Capacity
- PWP : Permanent Wilting Point

The following parameters are derived by the model:

- AW : Available Water
- Lx : Water Capacity of Layer x (1-5)
- SWx : Available Water in Layer x (1-4)

In the original MAFF model AW was 125mm. Layer 1 (100% ETo) was the first 50mm, layer 2 (50% ETo) was the second 50mm and layer 3 (25% ETo) was 25mm. This gave proportions of 2:2:1. In this model we vary AW but preserve the proportions from the original model. For example, if AW = 150mm then we would proportion the layers 60mm/60mm/30mm.

The following are the daily inputs to the model:

- P : Precipitation
- ETo : Potential Ref. Evapotranspiration (Priestly-Taylor method)

Other Values calculated by the model:

- ET : Evapotranspiration (Actual)
- SuWx : Surplus Water Above FC at stage x
- RO : Surface Run-off
- DR : Drainage

The soil water balance model produces a location specific daily profile containing estimates of:

- Date
- Actual Evapotranspiration
- Surplus Water Above FC (0 days)
- Surplus Water Above FC (-1 day)
- Surplus Water Above FC (-2 days)
- Soil Water Layer 1
- Soil Water Layer 2
- Soil Water Layer 3
- Soil Water Layer 4 (AD – PWP)

- Surface Runoff
- Drainage

SM3 Figure 3 PL/SQL Design

Sub EnterSoil(W, SW, LC)

newSW = min[LC, SW+W] // Calc soil water
 W = W - (newSW - SW) // Calc amt left over
 return W, newSW

EndSub

Sub ServiceET(W, ETo, ET, ETadj)

newET = min(W, ETo) // Calc ET at 100%
 adjET = newET * ETadj // Calc ET at adj
 ETo = ETo - newET // Calc remaining ETo
 W = W - adjET // Calc remaining water
 ET = ET + adjET // Calc new total ET
 return W, ETo, ET

EndSub

SM3 Figure 4 PL/SQL Design – Subroutines

SM4 References:

- MAFF (1967) Potential transpiration. MAFF Tech Bull No. 16. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food.
 MAFF (1971). The significance of winter rainfall over farmland in England and Wales. MAFF Tech Bull No. 24. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food.
 Met. Office (1981). The climate of the agricultural areas of Scotland. Climatological Memorandum No. 108. P.E. Francis. UK Meteorological Office.
 Monteith, J. L. (1965). Evaporation and Environment. Symposia of the Society for Experimental Biology. 19: 205–234

10 Supplementary Material 5: Observed trends and future climate projections for Scotland.

The following illustrations of observed trends and future climate projections are taken from Rivington and Jabloun (2022): hutton.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/D2_1a-Climate-trends-summary-report-FINAL-6-12-22.pdf

Further examples of visualisations of observed trends and climate projections for Scotland, along with agrometeorological indicators and climate summaries as time series animations (1960-2080) are available here: [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#)

Mean monthly precipitation change over the historical period 1990-2019 as compared to the baseline period 1960-1989

SM5 Figure 1 Relative change (%) in mean monthly precipitation between the 1960 – 1989 baseline period and 1990 – 2019 period.

Mean monthly maximum temperature change over the historical period 1990-2019 as compared to the baseline period 1960-1989

SM5 Figure 2 Change in mean monthly maximum temperature change between the 1960 – 1989 baseline period and 1990 – 2019.

Mean monthly minimum temperature change over the historical period 1990-2019 as compared to the baseline period 1960-1989

SM5 Figure 3 Change in mean monthly minimum temperature change between the 1960 – 1989 baseline period and 1990 – 2019

Future projections

Here we present visualisation of analysis of all 12 UKCP18 climate projections.

The monthly precipitation anomaly (SM5 Figure 4) representing the whole of Scotland shows there has been an overall increase in precipitation between 1990 – 2019 compared to the 1960 - 1989 baseline, except in September, which has become drier. The mean of the projections for next few decades to 2050 indicate Scotland’s climate to be wetter in December (c10%), January (c. 10%), February (45 – 55%) and April (25%) but less so in March (c. 5%). These projected changes align with the observed changes already seen.

SM5 Figure 4 Percent change in the national mean monthly precipitation compared to the 1960-1989 baseline for three time periods. Solid lines: 1990 – 2019 (red, observed data); 2020 – 2049 (green) and 2050 – 2079 (blue) mean of the 12 climate projections. Shaded areas represent the variation between the 12 projections. Note: the 0 line represents the 1960-1989 baseline.

To capture the general response across all 12 UKCP18 climate projections, we have produced ‘agreement maps’ on the direction of change in precipitation, where all 12 UKCP18 projections agree on the direction of change.

Change direction agreement for mean monthly precipitation over the period 2020-2049 for at least 12 ensemble members

Change direction agreement for mean monthly precipitation over the period 2050-2079 for at least 12 ensemble members

SM5 Figure 5 Agreement maps for all 12 projections on the direction of change in mean monthly precipitation for the 2020 – 2049 (top) and 2050 – 2079 (bottom) periods.

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